

Food frequency

Veillez remplir le questionnaire ci-dessous.

Merci !

How often do you eat bread? (ex: baguette bread, marmitte bread, coconut bread, sandwich bread)

- Never or rarely
- Less than once a day
- About 1 to 3 times a day
- About 4 to 5 times a day
- About 6 times a day or more

What type of bread do you USUALLY eat?

- Brown (multigrain, wholemeal)
- White
- Other
- Not sure

How often do you have butter or margarine (ex:Meadowlea) on your bread or rolls?

- Never
- Not very often
- Sometimes
- Almost always
- Always

How much milk (in total) do you USUALLY drink each day? (This includes all types of milk including flavoured milk and milk on cereal.)

- I don't drink milk
- Less than one cup a day
- About 1 to 2 cups a day
- About 2 to 3 cups a day
- 3 cups or more a day

How many serves of vegetables do you USUALLY eat each day? (A 'serve' is a half- cup of cooked vegetables or 1 cup of salad vegetables).

- I don't eat vegetables
 - About 1 serve or less
 - About 2 serves
 - About 3 serves
 - About 4 serves
 - About 5 serves or more
- (This includes all fresh, dried, frozen and tinned vegetables, but not tubers, potatoes, yams, sweet potatoes...)

How many serves of fruit do you USUALLY eat each day? (for exemple, papaya, banana, mangue, orange, apple, etc.)

- I don't eat fruit
 - About 1 serve or less
 - About 2 serves
 - About 3 serves
 - About 4 serves or more
- (This includes all fresh, dried, frozen, and tinned fruit.)

How much water do you USUALLY drink each day? This can be plain tap water or bottled water.

- I don't drink water
 - Less than one cup a day
 - About 1 cup a day
 - About 2 cups a day
 - About 3 cups a day
 - About 4 cups a day
 - About 5 cups a day
 - About 6 cups a day
 - About 7 cups a day
 - About 8 cups a day
 - About 9 cups a day
 - About 10 cups a day or more
- (1 average bottle = 2 cups)

How much soft drinks do you USUALLY drink (juice, soda, limonade, coke, etc.)?

- I don't drink juice
- Less than 1 cup a week
- About 1 - 3 cups per week
- About 4 - 6 cups per week
- About 1 - 2 cups a day
- About 2 - 3 cups a day
- About 3 cups or more a day

How often do you eat cheese?

- Never or rarely
- Less than once a week
- About 1 to 3 times a week
- About 4 to 6 times a week
- About once a day
- About 2 times a day or more

How often do you eat yoghurt?

- Never or rarely
- Less than once a week
- About 1 to 3 times a week
- About 4 to 6 times a week
- About once a day
- About 2 times a day or more

How often do you eat breakfast cereal? (ready-made, home-made or cooked)

- Never or rarely
- Less than once a week
- About 1 to 3 times a week
- About 4 to 6 times a week
- About once a day
- About 2 times a day or more

How often do you eat rice?

- Never or rarely
- Less than once a week
- About 1 to 3 times a week
- About 4 to 6 times a week
- About once a day
- About 2 times a day or more

How often do you eat pasta?

- Never or rarely
- Less than once a week
- About 1 to 3 times a week
- About 4 to 6 times a week
- About once a day
- About 2 times a day or more

How often do you eat baked beans, three bean mix, lentils, split peas, or dried beans?

- Never or rarely
- Less than once a week
- About 1 to 2 times a week
- About 3 to 4 times a week
- About 5 to 6 times a week
- Everyday

How often do you eat roots and tubers (taro, yams, sweet potatoes, etc.)?

- Never or rarely
- Less than once a week
- About 1 to 2 times a week
- About 3 to 4 times a week
- About 5 to 6 times a week
- Everyday

How often do you eat red meat such as beef, lamb, goat, pork, deer?

- Never or rarely
 - Less than once a week
 - About 1 to 2 times a week
 - About 3 to 4 times a week
 - About 5 to 6 times a week
 - Everyday
- (Include all steaks, chops, roasts, mince, stir fries and casseroles.)

How often do you eat chicken?

- Never or rarely
- Less than once a week
- About 1 to 2 times a week
- About 3 to 4 times a week
- About 5 to 6 times a week
- Everyday

How often do you eat fish?

- Never or rarely
- Less than once a week
- About 1 to 2 times a week
- About 3 to 4 times a week
- About 5 to 6 times a week
- Everyday

How often do you eat eggs?

- Never or rarely
- Less than once a week
- About 1 to 2 times a week
- About 3 to 4 times a week
- About 5 to 6 times a week
- About once a day
- About 2 times a day or more

How often do you eat canned meat ?

- Never or rarely
- Less than once a week
- About 1 to 2 times a week
- About 3 to 4 times a week
- About 5 to 6 times a week
- Everyday

How often do you eat traditional meals eaten in your family or community prepared for specific occasions?

- Never or rarely
- Less than once a week
- About 1 to 2 times a week
- About 3 to 4 times a week
- About 5 to 6 times a week
- Everyday

How often do you eat meat products such as sausages, hot dogs, ham, devon, sausage rolls, salami, meat pies, chicken nuggets or bacon?

- Never or rarely
- Less than once a week
- About 1 to 2 times a week
- About 3 to 4 times a week
- About 5 to 6 times a week
- Everyday

How often do you USUALLY have noodle soup (maggi, yum-yum etc.)?

- Never or rarely
- Less than once a week
- About 1 to 2 times a week
- About 3 to 4 times a week
- About 5 to 6 times a week
- Everyday

After school, how many days a week do you usually buy something to eat on the way home from school?

- Everyday
- 4 days per week
- 3 days per week
- 2 days per week
- 1 day per week
- Never or rarely

Do you buy food or beverages before or after school?

- Before school
 - After school
 - I don't buy any food nor beverages before or after school
- (Check the options telling when you buy something.)

Please list the 3 most common items you buy before school.

Please list the 3 most common items you buy after school.
